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Domestic Safety: Its Implications for Health Education

¹Princewill Chikakpobi Chukwure
princechukwure@gmail.com

²Foluke Temidola Abioye
foludola@yahoo.com

&

³Nkoli Ogechukwu Elem
contactnk15@yahoo.com

^{1,3} Rivers State College of Health Science & Management Technology
Oro-Owo Rumueme, Port Harcourt

²Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education,
Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt
princechukwure@gmail.com

Abstract

Domestic safety which is popularly known as home safety is an important aspect of health and safety education that needs to be practiced by all family members in Nigeria since there is a concern that nearly one million people over the age of 65 and below are treated in hospital emergency rooms for injuries associated with products and hazards found in their own homes. Domestic safety prevents home accidents which include drowning, poisoning, burns, cut, falls, strips and slips. It also protects life and encourages longevity. Domestic safety can be achieved through health and safety education which encourages and educates people on the hazards seen at home and help to change their behaviour towards these hazards. Domestic safety can be actualized through public awareness, educating people in their gathering places, educating students and pupils in their various schools and making domestic safety an important subject.

Keywords: domestic safety, education, health, implications